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Editorial

BEATITUDES: VALUES TO BE FULLY HUMAN

The Sermon on the Mount, the heart of Jesus' teaching, is acclaimed as the greatest speech in the history of humanity. The Beatitudes are the beginning and the summary of the Sermon on the Mount. Mahatma Gandhi was highly inspired by the Sermon on the Mount and by the Beatitudes.

Civil Rights leader John Lewis says, "If humankind would only live by the words of Jesus in the Beatitudes, the world would finally be at peace with itself." If we want to know what the heart of God is like, we have to look no further than the Beatitudes. Beatitudes are basically values and attitudes *to be, to be truly human*.

Psychologist Eric Fromm and philosopher Gabriel Marcel make a distinction between 'being' and 'having.' For true happiness, to be truly human, one must 'be' rather than 'have.' 'To be' one strives for *interiority*; on the other hand those who wish 'to have,' they seek *externals* like possessions, prestige, and power.

In the Old Testament, Moses went up to Mount Sinai and he brought the Ten Commandments for the Israelites. In the

New Testament, Jesus went up to a mountain in Galilee and he taught the Beatitudes to the entire humanity. Beatitudes teach us how we can realize our full potential as human beings and bring heaven on the earth.

We all know the Ten Commandments, which are in a way the essence of the Old Testament, but how many of us know the beatitudes, the essence of Jesus' teaching in the New Testament? Fr. Fio Mascarenhas SJ in his book *Unpacking the Good News* writes that most Catholics are sacramentalized, some catechised, but very few are evangelized. We need to evangelize ourselves and the future generation in the values of Christ. It is paramount that we deeply reflect on the eight beatitudes, and learn the values, which are most dear to Jesus' heart.

1. Blessed are the poor in spirit for theirs is the kingdom of heaven (Mt 5:3)

Although Lucan beatitudes speak about material poverty, the first Matthean beatitude does not speak about economic poverty. Being poor in spirit is being *dependent* on God for everything. It means trusting and relying on God for every step and every breath, we take. This dependence on God for all things is the hallmark of Psalmic spirituality. The righteous *anawim* totally trust in the Lord and seek refuge in him; but the wicked trust in their riches and seek refuge in wealth (Ps 52:7).

The first beatitude teaches us the *value of humility*. Humility comes from the Latin word *humus*, meaning soil or mud. The word 'human' comes from the same root because the first being Adam was made of *adamah*, the earth (Gen 2:7). We are earthlings, moulded out of the mud of the earth. Humility is the most basic of all virtues because to be humble is to be human. According to St. Ignatius of Loyola, all virtues flow from humility; on the other hand, all vices flow from pride. In humility, we attribute everything to God: all that we have and all that we are is God's. God has given it all to us and to God must we give all.

2. Blessed are those who mourn, for they will be comforted (Mt 5:4)

Mourning is not a killjoy attitude. This beatitude does not invite us to be sad saints, going around with long faces. On the other hand, it is a call to do a thorough reflection on our spiritual, social, political situation of woundedness, brokenness, and darkness, and feel deeply sorry for this fallen state. It is an appeal to mourn for our sins and the sins in the world, in its many manifestations.

The second beatitude teaches us the value of *repentance*. We have gone away from God, we have forgotten God, the source of all life, love, and goodness. We have betrayed God, and we have abused and misused his gifts and blessings. The repentant mourning encourages us to take a U-turn and come back to God, surrendering ourselves to his will; attributing everything to him and relying completely on him. This is exemplified in the Jesus' proclamation of the Reign of God in the Gospel of Mark: "Repent and believe in the Gospel" (Mk 1:15).

3. Blessed are the meek, for they will inherit the Earth (Mt 5:5)

We try to study many subjects and earn many degrees from renowned institutions. However, as Christians we should all learn two important subjects from the school of the Sacred Heart of Jesus. These two subjects are gentleness and humility. Jesus is our Master, and he himself invites us to learn these subjects from him (Mt 11:29).

The third beatitude teaches us the value of *gentleness* and *tenderness*. Being meek is not being passive but having the goodwill to change a bad situation into better. We do not return evil for evil, but we always show gentleness even to those who are harsh to us. This beatitude is reflected in the call of Pope Francis to bring a *revolution of tenderness* within and around us.

4. Blessed are those who hunger and thirst for righteousness, for they will be filled (Mt 5:6)

Righteousness in the Bible is all about relationship. Righteous are those who are in *right relationship* with God, self, nature, and others. They are passionate about creating a just world where everyone is treated with respect and dignity.

The fourth beatitude teaches us the value of *standing for justice for the marginalized and for the mother earth*. Fr. Stan Swamy and Sr. Rani Maria who gave up their lives fighting for the rights of the tribals are shining examples before us. They made the quest for justice their food and drink, and did not rest content until their last breath.

5. Blessed are the merciful for they will receive mercy (Mt 5:7)

The name of God is mercy. In his papacy, Pope Francis highlighted the mercy of God, especially when he announced the extraordinary Jubilee of Mercy in 2016. Being merciful is becoming merciful as our heavenly Father (Lk 6:36), which entails not being judgemental (Lk 6:37). This beatitude calls us to forgive and not to harbour grudges in our hearts. We are also called to open our hearts to the poor as the Latin word for mercy is *misericordia*, i.e., to have a heart for the poor.

The fifth beatitude teaches us to develop the value of *non-judgemental forgiveness*. The Hebrew word for mercy is *rechamim*, which literally means womb. Enamoured by this characteristic of God, the famous author, Fr. Anthony de Mello SJ would call God wombish God. We are also called to be tenderly loving and forgiving like our merciful motherly God.

6. Blessed are the pure in heart for they will see God (Mt 5:8)

Children are endowed with a gift of pure and innocent hearts. As we grow up, this childlike purity gets tarnished and hence Jesus invites his disciples to become like children.

He categorically says, “unless you change and become like children, you will never enter the kingdom of heaven” (Mt 18:3).

The sixth beatitude teaches us the value of *childlikeness*. Becoming like children is our project. Childlikeness is not childishness. Childlikeness is a trusting dependence, and serene abandonment in the arms of God. It is not an achievement, but graceful reception of blessedness from God the Father.

7. Blessed are the peacemakers, for they will be called children of God (Mt 5:9)

According to St. Mother Teresa of Calcutta, “The fruit of silence is prayer, the fruit of prayer is faith; the fruit of faith is love; the fruit of love is service, the fruit of service is peace.” Biblical *Shalom*, which means completeness, is the ultimate gift we aspire for. God gives us peace even in the midst of storms.

The seventh beatitude teaches us the value of *reconciliation*. We receive peace from Lord Jesus, the Prince of Peace and in turn become peacemakers. We courageously enter into the stormy situations and with the power of the Holy Spirit transform hatred into love, injury into pardon, despair into hope.

8. Blessed are those who are persecuted for righteousness' sake, for theirs is the kingdom of heaven (Mt 5:10)

The first seven beatitudes are simple statements, but after the eighth beatitude, which is a double-beatitude (Mt 5:10-11), Jesus gives us an imperative, a command to rejoice and be glad (Mt 5:12). Saints perceive persecution as a gift from God, which calls for rejoicing. A story from the life of Francis of Assisi is enlightening. Once Francis and Bruno had gone for a walk. Bruno asked Francis, “What would be the most joyful day in your life?” Francis answered, “On a rainy cold night, I come to my monastery and my brothers do

not recognize me; they beat me black and blue and throw me out. I am bruised and bleeding. That would be the happiest day of my life.”

The final beatitude teaches us the value of *suffering and cross*. In suffering and cross, we identify ourselves with our Saviour. Ultimately, by partaking into Jesus’ Paschal mystery, going through suffering, dying to ourselves, and carrying the cross daily, we become blessed.

CONCLUSION

Beatitudes teach us how to be fully human. Jesus is the fullest example of living the beatitudes. He is the happiest and the most blessed of the persons who walked the face of the Earth. In Jesus, God became human and lived out the beatitudes to show us how *to be* a fully human person. The values of humility, repentance, gentleness, justice, non-judgemental forgiveness, childlikeness, reconciliation, and suffering, enshrined in the beatitudes are mostly counter-cultural. Christians have to make them their way of life by constantly keeping the beatitudes in their hearts, reciting them to their children and talking about them when they are at home and when they are away, when they lie down and when they rise (Deut 6:6-7).

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Dr. Edwin RODRIGUES SJ
<edwinrods@gmail.com>